

MANAGEMENT QUALITY AND ITS SIGNIFICANT VARIABLES

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Abstract:

At the root of success in the tough competition, characterized by many unknowns which affect the way of business is conducted, is the quality of management. The universality of management is an undeniable reality, and its importance is all the more obvious as organizations become more complex.

This study focuses on some of the most important variables that condition the quality of management. The variables are multiple, but the most important ones refer to the quality of human resources, which is reflected in personal skills and qualities, and the quality of decisions made within the management activity. The quality of the information is added to them, since they represent the "raw material" of the foundation, adoption and operationalization and follow-up of managerial decisions. Moreover, doing effective business today involves providing the right information at the right time to the right people. Also particular importance are the quality of the managerial tools used and last, but not least, the quality of the procedural and structural organization. Improving the quality of management implies, on the one hand, attracting and keeping talented and competent employees in the company, it being known that performance is an exclusive result of the quality of the human factor. On the other hand, the decision-making system in the management of the organization needs a priority treatment, given the importance of the decision which remains the biggest source of business risk. Regarding the managerial tools, it is recommended to promote modern management systems, methods and techniques adapted to the needs of each organization, but also to the managerial functions for which they are used. Fundamental importance are here: decision-making decentralization, avoiding high specialization at the job level that generates routine and reducing the extent to which organizations are based on strict rules.

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JEL classification: M10, M12

1. Introduction

The managers and the organizations influence the society in which we live. It is well known that (Griffin, 2021) "although many people associate management primarily with large businesses effective management is more important in a small business which play an important role in the country's economy...In some respects, effective management is more important in a small business as in a large one". Along with the economic and social development, the management's objective knows a constant increase in complexity.

The quality of companies' management is an extremely important matter, as it influences to an overwhelming extent their capabilities to carry out their own productive activities and/or to market the products and services in an efficient, profitable manner, to bring their skills to fruition distinctiveness owned and to materialize them in competitive advantages. We can assert on full grounds that the factor that determines the success or failure of a company is represented by the quality of management. This determines the efficiency and effectiveness of management, but cannot be measured, to a large extent (Verboncu, 2018).

The quality of management resides in "the set of characteristics of the level at which a manager builds and coordinates the management system, realizes the management process and the organization's purpose, achieves its objectives, in conditions of effectiveness and efficiency"(Bezede, 2020). Some specialists (Russu, Dumitrescu & Pleșoianu, 2008) consider that, from the management quality's

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perspective, three categories of evaluation criteria of quality are important, namely: the evaluation criteria for managers' quality, the evaluation criteria for the organization's management quality and the one of the management's team evaluation.

Without pretending to have a detailed approach, however, we point out, in the following, some considerations in relation to some of the most important variables that explain the concept of quality management.

2. Some of the most important variables that explain the concept of management quality

In our opinion, the starting point in dealing with them must be the quality of the people in the organization, respectively, the managers and the executors. The success of any organization requires having the right people in the right places. It is well known that the human resource is involved in any type of organization, being its "soul", the most valuable asset. In an increasingly competitive business environment, the degree to which a company manages to attract and retain dedicated, efficient and responsible employees is fundamental to its success. Notable performances in terms of financial results, products or services offered are generated by the human resource (Iamandi, 2020). Today, human resource competence has a special relevance and becomes (Tudose, 2012) a nodal point of systemic transformations in society, in the economy and of course in the organization, and the ability of each company to attract, retain and develop the skills of its own employees is a prerequisite for obtaining competitive advantage.

Regarding the managers, in order to carry out activities such as exercising management functions as a process, leading people, decisions making whose application influences the activity and/or behavior of others, they must present some particularities (Burduş & Popa, 2018). As shown in the specialized literature (Prună, 2012), the manager's skills chart is an impact problem, and its solution equates to efficiency and effectiveness. In order to fulfill all of their very significant roles in organizations, managers must be competent, that is, they must have a whole arsenal of managerial and professional knowledge, qualities and skills. The distinguished specialist I. Verboncu (2018) shows that the managers' professionalism is essentially translated into the following:

- knowledge of the management processes' meaning and content and their functions and applying them in relation to the specificity of the managed field;
- active and responsible involvement in obtaining managerial and economic-financial performances;
- considering setting the objectives as the starting point of any action in which they are involved and the final allocation to people through a negotiation process, taking into account the official and personal authority of the job holders;
- receptive to change, capitalization of the favorable factors and trying to mitigate or even eliminate, if possible, resistance factors. Change is disruptive, but also unpredictable like people. It is produced through people, who must understand it in order to accept it;
- high creative-innovative capacity from the perspective of problem solving. As it is rightly stated (Ogrea & Herciu, 2022) "innovation (in its broadest sense has driven and accompanied the evolution of humankind since the dawn of time". Just like humans have adapted to their environment by identifying new and improved ways of organizing their work and the society, today's organizations must be innovative in order to survive. Generating new ideas and implementing them, are extremely valuable aspects for modern organizations, and regarding the employees the important aspects are satisfying the need of creativity and novelty becoming a source of job satisfaction. As shown in the specialized literature (Robbins & Coulter, 2016) "innovation means exploring new territory, taking risks, and doing things differently. And innovation isn't just for hightech or other technologically sophisticated organizations. Innovative efforts can be found in all types of organizations". Innovation is not related to the products, but is inextricably linked to progress (Christensen et al., 2017). Therefore, it is not at all surprising that

nowadays, managers are increasingly required to be innovative in defining objectives and in outlining the actions through which individual performance is not only defined, but also sustained. As a result, in the current context, the importance of developing in managers a behavior that values innovation, creativity and change is amplified;

- continuous learning and encouraging other members of the organization to do the same. The manager's role is to ensure that there is a high degree of learning in the organization. He must guide and support the employees learning efforts so that each one to increases the share of the learning activities, being aware that these processes will help them to carry out their activities to a higher level;
- conflict resolution skills and ensuring a favorable organizational climate. Change and conflict are equally universal in society. The relationships between people, those between them and the institutional-organizational environments of social life are not only generators of situations of motivation, satisfaction, emulation, but also of conflict-tense situations. It can be said that there is practically no organization without conflicts;
- have the ability to excel in both positions - manager and leader. Between a manager and a leader there is a deep difference and this should not be ignored, so that the company does not suffer. (Buckingham & Coffman, 2014). According to Lobonea Oltean (2012), "leaders are people who train and develop more conceptual skills (to see the organization as a whole, to know the place of each department, vision and strategic thinking, etc.) and human abilities (empathetic, charismatic, with a great communication skills and skills for understanding and influencing people and human groups)." The leader is the character who is concerned with establishing direct contacts, as frequent as possible, with the members of the group because only in this way can he really know people as they are, with their aspirations and interests.

In table 1 we observe some important elements that differentiate the concepts of management and leadership.

Table 1: A summary of the differences between management and leadership

Management	Leadership
It is performed over an activity (including the group that performs that activity). It mainly operates with structures and systems. It requires organizational skills. Requires extra attention to detail. It is based on authority (the right to influence other people). It is (1) a right (not any ability to influence) and (2) a possible (not necessarily effective) influence. It refers to an official position (function), formally established within a structure. It refers to an assigned position, entrusted by other people (even if this is done as a result of some own qualities). It pursues stability, it aims to preserve (maintain) a viable system. Its success it is conditioned by the leadership's success.	It is performed on a group of people. It operates with states of mind and interpersonal relationships. It requires psycho-social skills. It requires vision, above all else. It relies on influencing other people. It's about (1) a capacity (not necessarily a right) and (2) an effective influence (not just potential). It targets an official position (formal leadership) and an unofficial one (informal leadership). It refers to an assigned position (formal leadership), but also one earned through one's own behavior and personality (informal leadership). Follow the change, revolutionize, break with the past (that's how followers are won). Its success it is not conditioned by the management's success.

Source: Popa, M., Lungescu, & Salanță.(2013). *Management: concepts, techniques, skills*, Cluj University Press, p.270

We subscribe to the opinion of the specialists (Burduş & Popa, 2018) who consider that a successful company is one that has a high-performing leadership from the perspective of the quality of the adopted strategies, but also from the perspective of the human side, especially of boss-subordinate relationships. Such a company will have the ability to reinvent itself when environmental conditions demand it. But if the leadership is weak, both in terms of the human side and the strategies adopted, bankruptcy cannot be avoided and will occur, sooner or later.

Figure 1: Classification of companies by leadership competence

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The human side of the leadership	Reinvented Company	Entrepreneurial Company
	One of the 1000 companies selected by FORTUNE magazine	Company in BANKRUPTCY

Source: Burduş, E., Popa I.(2018). *Fundamentals of organization management.*(3rd edition). Pro Universitaria Publishing House. p.125

Undoubtedly, professional training of managers, experience, managerial skills are extremely important assets. Professional training includes (Russu, Dumitrescu & Pleşoianu, 2008) the basic training that is particularly important for lower and middle management levels, managerial training and instruction, but also the training that managers can carry out in areas that provide knowledge which could be used in managerial activity.

Regarding managerial skills, R.Katz (Lungescu, Popa & Salanţa, 2013) identified three categories of key skills that managers should have for the proper performance of their duties. It should be noted that the importance of some of these categories of skills varies depending on the different managerial positions on vertical:

- the technical skills aimed at the appropriate use of knowledge, methods, tools in a specific activity and which have a greater importance for operational managers, as they are people of action;
- human skills refer also to managers' ability to work with other people, with colleagues, subordinates or bosses. There are many categories of human skills. First of all, the manager must have collaboration skills, to work well in a team and emphasize its synergy. Communication skills are also in the category of human skills. Moreover, regardless of the field, they are important, communication being a vital component, essential for the organization's activity effectiveness. It is widely accepted that it is virtually impossible to identify any facet of a manager's job that does not involve communication. Only through good communication do managers fully understand the employees. On the other hand, managers' skills regarding motivation are of particular importance, since, in their absence, it is not possible to discuss the achievement of the desired performances both by the individual and by the organization. It is known that only genuine motivation is able to generate the feeling of usefulness, of professional value, but also the well-being of the individual and, on a broader level, of the organization. Moreover, it is known that in multinational corporations, employees of different ethnicities and cultures work together. Accordingly, acting on a global scale requires the ability to work effectively with people belonging to different cultures.

We can affirm that possessing the skills in this category is equally important for top, middle and operational managers.

- conceptual skills aim (Lalu, 2009) "the manager's ability to see the organization as a whole, to know the place of each department in the organization, of the organization in society, finally, the ability to think strategically, to take long-term decisions". Since top managers are the ones who need to have the most complete view of the organizational system, this key skill category targets them as a priority.

Another variable of particular importance is represented by the quality of the adopted decisions. Taking it into account is explained by the fact that the essential element, the tool of expressing managerial activity is, unequivocally, the decision. It is the essential element of a manager's daily activity. "Decision making is a course of action consciously chosen from available alternatives for the purpose of achieving the desired result. The process of decision-making is one of the most complex mechanisms of human thinking, as various factors and courses of action intervene in it, with different results. It is about making choices by identifying a decision, gathering information and assessing alternative solutions"(Omarli, 2017).

Today, the problems faced by organizations are extremely diverse. From this perspective ((Russu, Dumitrescu & Pleșoianu, 2008) managerial decisions of superior quality assume a thorough foundation ensured by the adequate information processing and the use of decision-making methods and techniques. From the perspective of the pace of change, this is, as is known, more alert, and the companies must respond effectively to changes. This implies an increased speed of decision-making reaction. In practice, the result of taking decisions too late or too slowly could be, for example, uncaptalization of the opportunities or losing employees or partners. It is also true that (Sayegh, Anthony& Perrewé, 2004) "Today's manager is increasingly expected to make decisions based on paradigms that depart from traditional rationality and information processing models. This is particularly so under crisis conditions, where there is little time and information available for choice consideration."

In our opinion, top managers should support and stimulate decision-making in groups or teams, because this approach presents a number of considerable advantages. Approaching the decision in a group allows to have access to multiple experiences, to more skills than could be found to one manager. Also, the group can elaborate and deliver multiple alternatives and proposes, and at the same time, different methods of implementation in practice. Moreover, the complexity of the world and the diversity of the environment we live in, require more options that must be identified and taken into account.

Regarding the quality of information used, it is no longer a secret that effective business involves providing the right information to the right people at the right time. Moreover, in the context of scientific and technological changes, information has become "a product that can be bought, sold or exchanged" (Creangă&Buzev, 2020) and it is absolutely necessary for them to rigorously meet the requirements' of quality and opportunity. The need of information it is located at the level of all departments, however, for the manager it is a vital demand because "he guides in his management activity by the received information" (Drăgan, 2019). Information has a vital role from the perspective of decision-making. On the other hand, the efficiency of completing the tasks that managers delegate depends on the quality and quantity of information that reaches the lower level.

The quality of management depends, to a large extent, on the quality of the tools used by the management, and the quality of it is given by the way in which the five managerial functions are exercised and facilitated by the systems, methods and techniques used by the management. These must be adapted to the needs of each organization. In Table 2, we present (Verboncu, 2018) some managerial tools that contribute to ensuring high-quality decisions adopted within the perimeter of each managerial function.

Table 2: Managerial tools with important contributions in ensuring a high quality of decisions adopted within the perimeter of managerial functions

Management function	Management tools
Prediction	management by objectives, management based on profit centers, management by exceptions, diagnosis, SWOT analysis, dashboard, job description
Organizing	organization chart, process map, organization and operation regulations, delegation, decision sheets, job description
Coordination	delegation, meeting, organization and operation regulations
Staffing	management by objectives, management by exceptions, job description, delegation, management based on centers of profit
Controlling -evaluation	dashboard, diagnosis, job description, SWOT analysis, management by exceptions, management by objectives, management based on centers of profit

Source: Verboncu, I. (2018). *How do we lead? : between amateurism and professionalism*. University's Publishing House. p.410

From the perspective of the procedural and structural organization quality, in the opinion of the aforementioned specialist, are relevant, especially:

- the delimitation and dimensioning with a high degree of accuracy of the procedural components, correspondingly, of tasks, attributions, activities and functions;
- the delimitation and dimensioning with a high degree of accuracy of the structural-organizational components, in particular, the jobs and compartments;
- human endowment of the jobs and departments, from the quality point of view (qualification level), but also quantity;
- a balanced and reasonable dimensioning of management rules for managers located on the same hierarchical level. In this way, the tendency to overwork some of them is avoided;
- the orientation of organizational relations towards cooperative relations - determined, in particular, by the need to jointly elaborate some works or consultations on how to solve some problems, but also towards functional and non-hierarchical authority relations.

It should also be noted that in any organizational activity, the balance between centralization and decentralization is decisive. It is found that the trend is towards decisional decentralization (Robbins & Coulter, 2016). Thus, more and more power is given to employees in making decisions, thus exploiting their ability to ensure through their decisions the reduction of resource consumption, the increase of profit and the value of the company.

3. Conclusions

There is only one conclusion, but of fundamental importance and complexity, namely that the quality of management - the essence of modern management performance is conditioned by numerous variables and requires a new approach and special efforts.

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